

Title (EN/DE)

Using Bibliographic Data for Historical Research – Two Workflows for the VD17 Catalogue
Bibliographische Daten für die historische Forschung – Zwei Workflows für den VD17 Katalog

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Abstract (EN/DE)

Library catalogues have been recognised as an important source for studying book production and knowledge exchange. The bibliographic data stored within them is increasingly regarded as research data for quantitative analysis. This data, however, presents researchers with challenges, since they are using it for purposes different from those originally intended. This paper identifies some of these challenges and presents the practical solutions used to address them through two exemplary workflows that leverage the potential of the *Verzeichnis der im deutschen Sprachraum erschienenen Drucke des 17. Jahrhunderts* (VD17), or German retrospective national bibliography for the seventeenth century. These workflows illuminate the ways in which the VD17 metadata standard and scholarly interventions to facilitate use of bibliographic data for historical research can shape our view of the past.

Bibliothekskataloge gelten als wichtige Quelle für die Erforschung der Buchproduktion und des Wissensaustauschs. Die darin gespeicherten bibliografischen Daten werden zunehmend als Forschungsdaten für quantitative Analysen herangezogen. Diese Daten stellen Forschende jedoch vor Herausforderungen, da sie für andere Zwecke als ursprünglich vorgesehen verwendet werden. Der vorliegende Beitrag identifiziert einige dieser Herausforderungen und stellt praktische Lösungen vor, die anhand von zwei beispielhaften Workflows umgesetzt wurden. Dabei nutzen sie das Potenzial des *Verzeichnisses der im deutschen Sprachraum erschienenen Drucke des 17. Jahrhunderts* (VD17), der deutschen retrospektiven Nationalbibliografie für das siebzehnte Jahrhundert. Diese Workflows veranschaulichen, wie der

Metadatenstandard des VD17 und wissenschaftliche Bemühungen die Nutzung dieser bibliografischen Daten in der historischen Forschung zu erleichtern unsere Sicht auf die Vergangenheit prägen können.

Keywords (EN/DE)

Bibliographic data, Workflows, Book history, Early modern, Text, Bibliographic data science
Bibliographische Daten, Workflows, Buchgeschichte, Frühe Neuzeit, Text, Bibliographic data science

1 Introduction

Bibliographic data, or metadata, is data about books and other information resources and has been created across centuries. Librarians and others responsible for collections began developing rules, or metadata schemas, for creating catalogues early on (Duncan 2021, 31–36). Thus, this data existed as structured data long before the digital transformation in handwritten or printed form, for instance in bibliographies, card catalogues, and inventories. Before the advent of mass digitisation, bibliographic data was migrated from analogue to digital format for the practical purpose of more easily finding the resources described. Even today, we have many more bibliographic records than digitised texts, and digitised page images than machine-readable full texts.

More recently, library catalogues have been recognised as an important source for studying book production and knowledge exchange, and the metadata stored within them is increasingly regarded as research data for quantitative analysis.¹ But the metadata also presents researchers with challenges, since they are using it for different purposes from those originally intended (Lahti et al. 2019). This paper identifies some of these challenges and presents the practical solutions used to address them through two exemplary workflows that leverage the potential of one specific catalogue for historical research – the *Verzeichnis der im deutschen Sprachraum erschienenen Drucke des 17. Jahrhunderts* (VD17).²

The VD17 is the German retrospective national bibliography for the seventeenth century, which includes all publications in the German language and any work printed in German-speaking countries in any language from 1601 to 1700. The Gemeinsamer Bibliotheksverbund (GBV), or Common Library Network, hosts the VD17 database and online catalogue, which currently contain over 315,000 items, many with links to digitised versions.³ Comparatively, the quality of the VD17 data exceeds that of many other national retrospective bibliographies of the early

¹ For an early example, see Jannidis 2002.

² This paper stems from a panel at the DARIAH Annual Event 2025, “How to Provide and Use Bibliographical Data for Research – the Example of the VD17” (Rissler-Pipka et al. 2025).

³ Plans currently exist to merge the VD17 with the VD16 and VD18 into a combined search portal for retrospective German national bibliography (VD17, Lauer et al. 2024). A regularly updated list of publications on or working with data from VD17 can be found at <http://www.vd17.de/en/about-the-project/publications/>.

modern period. The recording of “fingerprints”, which consist of characters that appear at specific positions on prescribed pages along with the year of publication, is but one example.⁴

There is much to consider beyond data quality, however, in working effectively with the VD17. Researchers need to familiarise themselves with the data format (K10plus PICA⁵), cataloguing standards (Regeln für die alphabetische Katalogisierung in wissenschaftlichen Bibliotheken, and Resource Description and Access⁶), catalogue-specific documentation (Arbeitsgemeinschaft Alte Drucke [AAD]⁷ and VD17 format documentation⁸), and migration history of the source database. They also need to be aware of its inevitable limitations, including completeness and geographical range (Beyer 2011, Lauer et al. 2024, 509–515). These limitations may impact the validity and significance of the results obtained by quantitative analysis and thus should be considered carefully.

Our paired workflows give steps for data identification, refinement, and validation that highlight the challenges encountered in using the VD17 as research data, as well as for addressing them for the purpose of analysis and interpretation. These workflows are intended to illuminate the ways in which the VD17 metadata standard, on the one hand, and scholarly interventions to facilitate use of bibliographic data for historical research, on the other, can shape our view of the past.

2 Workflow I: Detecting variant printings

The VD17, following rare book cataloging standards, records every variant of every book in library collections, down to single-character adjustments. However, for analytical purposes, it would often be useful to be able to make calculations at the level of print run, edition, or distinct intellectual work. To this end, we are developing a method to identify variants of a print run,⁹ print runs of an edition,¹⁰ editions, and works, all of which are reflected in an undifferentiated manner as records in the VD17. The workflow below addresses the first two scenarios to merge records in preparation for analyses at the level of print run and print runs of an edition. Work to refine the method is ongoing.

⁴ For a technical description of the practice, see Beyer 2019, and for a historical perspective, see Harris 2006. The VD17 uses the London-Oxford-Cambridge scheme (source code “fei”), which results in a 16-character set taken from four separate points in a book.

⁵ <https://wiki.k10plus.de/spaces/K10PLUS/pages/27361360/K10plus-Formatdokumentation>.

⁶ <http://www.vd17.de/datenbankinformation/katalogisierungsrichtlinie/>.

⁷ <https://verbundwiki.gbv.de/spaces/GAD/pages/52592643/Arbeitsgemeinschaft+Alte+Drucke+beim+GBV+und+SWB>.

⁸ <https://swbtools.bsz-bw.de/cgi-bin/k10plushelp.pl?katalog=VD17&cmd=index>.

⁹ May also include variants of an issue at the level of a print run, such as *Titelauflagen*.

¹⁰ May also be viewed as variants of an issue at the edition level, for instance a new print run with a new title page (re-issue).

We are deploying this method to identify and analyse publications associated with members of the *Fruchtbringende Gesellschaft*, or Fruitbearing Society, in the VD17.¹¹ The Society was the largest and most important academy in seventeenth-century Central Europe (Ball 2008, Conermann et al. 2017). Our analyses are targeted to research questions of historiographical interest by extracting meaning about members' publishing patterns and their social and intellectual connections (e.g. Mäkelä et al. 2024).¹²

Our work is wide-ranging and measures members' intellectual production, intellectual and social connectivity, and the economic activity related to their publications. Thus, it is key that we work with the VD17 metadata at a level that is meaningful to the research question at hand. In some cases, this is at the level of a print run, which was largely printed from the same setting of type, and in others an edition, which was largely printed from a new setting of type. In both cases, the core text, as the main intellectual contribution of the author, remains largely the same. Yet others require consideration of different editions, for example printed at a later date or in a different place, which generally indicates a substantive change in intellectual content.

These conceptual categories do not necessarily align with the VD17 standard or its original intention. In the handpress era, multiple variant printings could easily be generated during a print run. Included are common variants such as minor corrections to the text under press, changes to the front and back matter, and a new title pages appended to a previously published issue (*Titelaufgaben*¹³); as well as less common ones, such as an issue planned with different title pages for different publishers who shared in the costs (*éditions partagées*) or from the same setting of type on larger paper (*Formataufgaben*).

The VD17 standard specifies that these printings be recorded separately if variation exists in the index pages, extent, or fingerprint. Practically, this means that minor adjustments made during a print run – down to single-character modifications – can result in multiple records in the VD17. Recording variants at this level of granularity is important for the VD17's original purpose as a

¹¹ Work on the *Fruchtbringende Gesellschaft* in the VD17 (FG in VD17) project has been carried out with support from the Herzog August Bibliothek Wolfenbüttel, Fulbright Finland, University of Colorado Boulder Center for Humanities and Arts and Research and Innovation Office, and University of Helsinki Institute for Social Sciences and Humanities. Thanks to the following individuals who assisted in the research and data enhancement process: Julius Arnold, Narges Azizifard, Gabriele Ball, Andreas Herz, and Erik Radio; and to Die deutsche Akademie des 17. Jahrhunderts: *Fruchtbringende Gesellschaft* project for its invaluable foundational work on the Society.

¹² Lindquist et al. in press is an example of the type of conclusions one can reach about the social and intellectual connections the Society fostered among members as seen through the lens of their publications in the VD17. This workflow supported that work through merging variants belonging to an edition as a discrete intellectual contribution by the author and allows us to calculate the number of connected people and their roles in the publication at a level that is meaningful for the purposes of reporting.

¹³ Publishers might diversify their stock by trading copies of their own publications for those printed by another, who then appended a new title page with their own imprint, or they might sell leftover copies from their own stock with a title page that was better aligned with current buyer interests. Occasionally, this practice was illicitly employed to pass the work off as a new edition.

retrospective national bibliography. But for our historical research, these variant records often serve as an analytical confounder, and they are often difficult to detect.¹⁴

Grouping bibliographic records using the heuristic outlined above allows us to more accurately analyse and interpret an author's intellectual contribution and undertake differential economic analyses that could not be accommodated otherwise. The existence of multiple print runs of an edition can serve as a proxy for new investment in and presumably demand for an edition (Munck 2019). Thus, if a member authors a publication aligned with the Society's programmatic agenda and it goes into multiple print runs, this generally indicates wider interest in and circulation of these ideas.

Sigmund von Birken's *Eigentliche Beschreibung...des Fried- und Freudenmahls Schauspiel und Feuerwerks* (1650) illustrates how merging variants can impact analysis. This publication describes the peace celebrations that Imperial plenipotentiary Ottavio Piccolomini, Duke of Amalfi hosted in Nürnberg in 1650. It is an example of the peace literature that brought Birken fame and aligns closely with the Society's irenic stance.¹⁵ The multiple VD17 records associated with this publication give the immediate impression of brisk publisher investment and keen interest in the content. After our method was applied, however, these were all identified as variants of the same print run springing from minor corrections in the text under press.¹⁶ Merging variants like these, rather than treating them as separate print runs, is an important step in right-sizing our data to achieve a more accurate understanding of the market dynamics and potential impact of a member publication.¹⁷

¹⁴ Very large datasets can use print run proxies, e.g. by grouping like works by publication year. This approach, however, is too blunt for our more circumscribed analytical dataset, which requires greater accuracy.

¹⁵ These publications are associated with the *Pegnesischer Blumenorden*, a literary society modeled on the *Fruchtbringende Gesellschaft*. Due to crossover in membership and aims, they are included in our analytical set.

¹⁶ These heuristics of course can fail at times, due to the complexity of some of the printing cases.

¹⁷ In contrast, Birken's separately published peace play, *Teutscher Kriegs Ab- und Friedens Einzug* (1650), which was performed at the same celebration and is included in the publication above, proved to be more successful. It has six associated VD17 records, which were identified as print runs. The standalone play thus drew a higher level of investment and interest than the first publication did not.

Figure 1: Image alluding to peace in the Empire from half-title page of Sigmund von Birken's *Eigentliche Beschreibung* (1650). Bayerische Staatsbibliothek (BSB) München, 4 P.o.germ. 119.

The workflow described below is an important step in our pipeline to transform the VD17 catalogue data to fit-for-purpose research data. It will have reuse value for researchers who require similar levels of expressiveness about the printing history of works from this data to answer their research questions. The steps are iterative and a part of a cycle of ongoing improvement of our data and code that is responsive to project needs. At this point, the data acquisition and preprocessing steps have already taken place (Tolonen et al.).¹⁸

¹⁸ At any time, an up-to-date version of the VD17 data is available via the SRU protocol, discussed in more detail in section 3.1 below, from <http://www.vd17.de/en/about-the-vd-17-online-catalogue/sru/>. Our export format is PICA-XML, which we convert using <https://github.com/hsci-r/bibxml2> to TSV/Parquet and version through Git at <https://github.com/hsci-r/vd17-data/>.

Figure 2: VD17 variant workflow

2.1 Refinement

Variants of a print run are not consistently identified in the VD17 data. The best indication that exists is an occasional statement in a record's notes field that the publication is not identical to another.

To merge variants of a print run, we developed the capability to map records together based on:

- Cataloguer notes that one record is not identical to another (typically indicating that the documents are variants, since the note would not be necessary otherwise)
- Fingerprints (ideally, identical fingerprints indicate that the documents are variants/of the same print run)
- Titles, places of publication, printers/publishers, years of publication, and extents of printings (may be used to map print runs, editions, or works)¹⁹

Gerhard Dünnhaupt's massive bio-bibliography of authors of the German Baroque was an important source of information for enriching and verifying bibliographic information in this process (Dünnhaupt 1990).

2.2 First-round validation

To measure the quality of the results, we conducted a preliminary validation on a test set of 200 records focusing on the second and third methods for variant detection. Since the explicit cataloguer notes in VD17 records were considered a gold standard, we decided more

¹⁹ The exact details of the pipeline are complex and a work in progress; however, the current version is available at https://github.com/hsci-r/fbs-analysis/blob/main/src/create_unified_data.Rmd.

actionable insight could be gained from determining how well the other two approaches complemented them for this task.

Our evaluation determined that a better F-measure²⁰ for variant printings is obtained by using both methods together. Also, it showed that an identical fingerprint only goes so far in identifying these printings, as they are sourced only from the first 13 or 17 pages of the main text; thus, identical fingerprints can arise for different editions when content is revised or added beyond that point in the text but the beginning remains unaltered. Further, we found that ~20% of pairs with identical fingerprints were not variants of the same print run. Adding a further requirement that the number of pages between candidates for variant status needed to be nearly equal (within a margin of maximum ± 3 difference in page counts) remedied this source of error, leading to 100% precision in the test set. At the same time, the fingerprints were identical in only 55% of variant cases, which validated the need to use complementary approaches in variant identification.

Our variant detection method at this point flagged 13% of the records in the VD17 as variants. The percentage varied significantly over time, between ~10-14%, and even more between genres (based on genre terms drawn from the AAD controlled vocabulary), between ~2-60%.²¹ This outcome indicates that variant detection is important for temporal and genre analyses, at the very least.

2.3 Analysis as impetus for refinement

Analysis for a particular use case often exposes issues of bias and data quality that drive further refinement to improve the data for research use. In the case of merging variants, this process was sparked by analyzing network connections among Society members in the publications.²² We noticed that some variants were not being caught because the cataloguer notes portion of our variant detection process was deactivated when we rebuilt our research data pipeline for better flexibility, transparency, and reproducibility.

One of the improvements made to the pipeline was implementation of a changelog that rendered changes to the analytical dataset more transparent when algorithmic changes were applied. When the missing notes portion was reactivated, the changelog output offered the opportunity to perform a second validation to ensure that records were being merged in line with our expectations. It also triggered rethinking our guidelines for print runs and editions, which we previously had treated as one and the same (Gaskell 1972, Mäkelä et al. 2024).

2.4 Second-round validation

²⁰ The F-measure is a standard measure for the performance of computational systems in tasks like these, defined as the harmonic mean of precision – the proportion of detected matches that are correct, and recall – the proportion detected by the methods of the true matches identified manually.

²¹ <https://uri.gbv.de/terminology/aadgenres/>. See also Sommer 2010.

²² Christoph Boveland has shown the VD17 data to be well-adapted to this method (Boveland 2015).

To assess how well our method performed in detecting print runs and editions, we conducted a second validation on all variant groupings identified in the changelog, plus a random sample of additional variant groupings already existing in our analytical dataset. This set totaled 62 groupings, nearly half of those in our analytical set.²³

The analysis showed that our method was better at matching editions (100%) than print runs (71-76%). In ~72% of cases of mismatched print runs, the fingerprints varied. The most common pattern showed variation in the third or fourth fingerprint groupings, which were likely to be sourced from the main text as opposed to prefatory material.

Our analysis also indicated that the cataloguer notes were less accurate for identifying print runs than editions. For example, one print run of *Chymische Hochzeit Christiani Rosencreutz* (1616, 23:279666R), attributed to Johann Valentin Andreae, was erroneously grouped with another (1616, 30:754854N and 23:000604B), though they have completely different fingerprints, based on a cataloguer note. Thus, the variant detection process for print runs could potentially benefit from refinement to see if recall for print runs could be improved. The logical next step would be to test a process whereby the fingerprints of records with cataloguer notes are compared with one another, and – if a significant threshold of difference is detected – flagged for manual evaluation to determine whether they are from the same print run.

The workflow for detecting variant printings described above can be adapted for a variety of analyses using VD17 data where print runs and editions are more relevant units of analysis for the research questions under investigation. Tracking substantial changes to intellectual content and financial investment in publications are two common bibliographic research scenarios. Indeed, the rationale behind defining print runs and editions may also provide an intellectual basis for applications to other bibliographic data sources that record printings on a more granular basis than is required for analysis.

3 Workflow II: Building a corpus of full texts using genres in VD17

In the second of our workflows, the VD17 serves as a means to find and acquire a specific corpus of data.²⁴ This use case is much more in line with the original intention for which the bibliographic data was created: to find data to be analysed, i.e. the texts stored in printed books or their digital representations. Even in this case, the VD17 metadata is invaluable to contextualising and interpreting the texts to be analysed.

This workflow takes *Theatrum Europaeum*, a 21-volume chronicle of the contemporary history of seventeenth and early eighteenth-century Europe, originally published between 1633 and

²³ Currently ~8% of records in our analytical set (131 / 1698) and ~7% in the VD17 (20,340 / 285,084) are variant groupings, reducing the overall number of the latter by over 30,000 records.

²⁴ For the code and data used in this workflow, see the following GitHub-repository: https://github.com/mgoermer/workflow_vd17_IIIF. It is also available in Zenodo (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20058464](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20058464)) and includes further documentation on the technical aspects of the workflow.

1738 (Roßbach et al. 2012), as a starting point.²⁵ Of course, the authors of this chronicle used and compiled many sources, among them trade fair reports, or *Meßrelationen*, early modern precursors of newspapers that were published semi-annually at the trade fairs in Frankfurt am Main and Leipzig (Körber 2016). This approach was already described in earlier studies, most notably by Bingel (1909) and more recently by Lauert (2025), but it can be studied far more comprehensively using digital methods. As a first step to do so, we provide a workflow to compile and download a corpus of OCR texts of *Meßrelationen* and discuss potential scenarios for further analysis on the basis of a comparison between this corpus and the first volume of *Theatrum Europaeum* (Abelinus 1635) covering the years 1618 to 1629.

3.1 Querying the VD17 to compile a corpus based on genres

To query the VD17 database and compile the corpus, we use the VD17's SRU API.²⁶ SRU (Search/Retrieve via URL) is, according to its home page on the Library of Congress website, “a standard XML-based protocol for search queries”.²⁷ It provides three operations: `explain`, `scan`, and `searchRetrieve` (Morgan 2004). For our use case, we only need to use the operations `explain` and `searchRetrieve`. The `explain` operation can be used to retrieve basic information about the database to be queried, in this case the VD17,²⁸ the technical specifications of the API, and the available search indexes. For our purposes, we use the indexes for genres²⁹ as well as those for the year of publication and specific library holdings.

With the help of the search indexes, we can query the SRU API via the `searchRetrieve` operation for *Meßrelationen* – the term *Meßrelation* appears in the AAD genre list used in the VD17 – published from 1618 to 1629, the timeframe covered by the first volume of *Theatrum Europaeum*. For practical reasons, we begin by limiting the search to *Meßrelationen* held by the BSB München and receive a response in XML that can be downloaded and saved locally.³⁰ In our case, the XML conforms to the Dublin Core standard, a lightweight metadata schema that is comparatively easy to understand and entirely sufficient for the next steps in the workflow. For other use cases, like that presented above, other standards supported by the VD17's SRU API, such as MARC21 or PicaXML, are more appropriate because they contain richer information. But they are also harder to understand if one is unfamiliar with bibliographic data and cataloguing standards.

²⁵ The following workflow was developed in preparation of a research proposal aimed at creating a digital edition of the whole *Theatrum Europaeum*. The proposal is a collaboration between the Herzog August Bibliothek Wolfenbüttel and the University of Vechta and intended to be submitted to the German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft [DFG]) in fall 2026 to secure funding for a long-term project.

²⁶ See for the following <http://www.vd17.de/datenbankinformation/sru/>.

²⁷ <https://www.loc.gov/standards/sru/>.

²⁸ See <https://sru.k10plus.de/vd17?operation=explain&version=2.0> or <https://sru.k10plus.de/vd17>.

²⁹ See n. 21.

³⁰ The resulting query URL is:

<https://sru.k10plus.de/vd17?version=2.0&operation=searchRetrieve&query=pica.gat=messrelation+and+pica.jhr=1618-1629+and+pica.bib=40004&maximumRecords=50&startRecord=1&recordSchema=dc>.

3.2 Downloading full texts using VD17 data

The second step of the workflow uses the BSB München's International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) API to obtain OCR texts for their *Meßrelationen*.³¹ IIIF is an open standard to make digital images available. A core element of the standard is the IIIF manifest, a JSON file that contains all relevant information about a digital object to be displayed in a IIIF viewer.³² This includes metadata and links to image files as well as to files containing the OCR text (Mertens 2021, section 3.2). In order to obtain the OCR texts, the XML result of the query above is parsed with an XSLT script that uses the IIIF manifests of the BSB München's digitised sources to download the OCR texts and save them as TXT files.³³ The script iterates through the XML and extracts the necessary information to access the manifest files via the BSB München's IIIF API. Then, it parses each manifest to find links to the OCR files for each page of a source document. In the case of the BSB, the OCR files are provided in XHTML, from which the raw text of the transcriptions can easily be extracted and saved as TXT files.

3.3 Corpus analysis using downloaded texts

Now that we have the corpus of text files, we can analyse them in different ways. The workflow was originally developed for the purpose of a stylometric comparison between the *Meßrelationen* and the first volume of *Theatrum Europaeum* (Abelinus 1635), using the package *stylo* for R (Eder et al. 2015). This analysis was a first attempt to test the hypothesis that the author of the first *Theatrum* volume, Johann Philipp Abelinus (1600–1634), only compiled his sources, including the *Meßrelationen*, without much intellectual input of his own. Although this hypothesis is admittedly old – it was revised by Bingel in the early twentieth century (1909, 28–32, 113–117) and most recently by Lauert (2025, 111–118, 144–148, 167–173, 205–211) – this comparison is still useful for testing the validity of digital methods, especially given the unavoidable OCR errors in the texts of our corpus.

Comparative analysis with *stylo*, therefore, can be regarded as a proof of concept for comparing single volumes or the entire run of *Theatrum* against the *Meßrelationen* and other sources. Based on the first volume, the analysis finds significant differences between the relevant *Meßrelationen* and *Theatrum*, the text of which was obtained in TEI-XML from the Herzog August Bibliothek Wolfenbüttel and divided into TXT files for each year (fig. 3).³⁴ These preliminary results reinforce Bingel's conclusion that sources were merely compiled in the *Meßrelationen* but were reworked in *Theatrum* (Bingel 1909, 32).

³¹ See the documentation here: <https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/interfaces>.

³² For an example of such a manifest file, see <https://api.digitale-sammlungen.de/iiif/presentation/v2/bsb10503608/manifest>.

³³ The script can be found here: https://github.com/mgoermar/workflow_vd17_IIIF/blob/main/download_ocr_bsb.xsl.

³⁴ <http://diglib.hab.de/periodica/70-a-hist-2f/tei-transcript.xml>. A slightly different version of the TEI-XML can be accessed via the Deutsches Textarchiv. See https://www.deutschestextarchiv.de/book/show/abelinus_theatrum_1635.

Figure 3: Stylometric comparison between volume one of *Theatrum Europaeum* and *Meßrelationen* via cluster analysis highlighting stylistic differences between and in both corpora as a tree diagram or stemma. The differences suggest that the author of the *Theatrum Europaeum*, Johann Philipp Abelinus, while incorporating many passages from *Meßrelationen* (see fig. 4), still followed his own narrative style in which he imbedded the acknowledged and unacknowledged citations from other sources.

Nevertheless, many text similarities still exist between the first volume of *Theatrum* and the *Meßrelationen*, including near-identical passages indicating text reuse. These passages can be identified using different programs, e.g. quid, a tool developed at the Humboldt-Universität Berlin.³⁵ Quid can be used to find occurrences of text reuse, and analyse as well as visualise them by providing a synoptic view of the main text and other texts to which the main text is compared (fig. 4).³⁶ Again, the results are promising given the fact that the *Meßrelation* texts, which contain an unknown number of OCR errors, were relatively successfully compared to the *Theatrum* double-keyed text, which in theory is circa 99,95% correct according to the information in the `teiHeader` of the TEI-XML file (see also Stäcker 2011, 114).

³⁵ <https://scm.cms.hu-berlin.de/schlueselstellen/quid>.

³⁶ For the visualization, see <https://scm.cms.hu-berlin.de/schlueselstellen/quidex-wh>.

J. Ph. Abelinus: *Theatrum Europaeum*, Bd. 1: 1621

Wird derogiren / noch dadurch dem Graffen einige Gerechtigkeit an vnserm Erbstatum Fürstenthumb zu wachsen können.

Vnd damit nun E. Keys. M. vnnd Ld. eygentliche Wissenschaft haben mögen / wie es mit solchem gehalten Fürsten Titul warhaftig beschaffen / vnd woren sie vom Graffen verleitet worden / so ist zwar nicht ohne / daß auß diesem Stammen etliche wenige zu Fürsten erhoben worden / welche aber nicht jetzige Graffen Progenitores, noch deren Brüdere / sondern in remotiori gradu lineae collateralis jhnen allein verwandt gewesen / vntr welchen **dann Graff Gerhardt der Dritte / der erste zum Hertzogen von Schleßwig von Woldimaro Anno 1326. erhöht / welcher aber hernacher das Hertzogthumb hinwiderumb abtretten / vnnd sich / wie auch seine Söhne / mit der Graffschafft Holstein vnd den Graffen Titul contentiren lassen müssen / biß auff Hertzog Erichen von Schleßwig (der der letzte von Canuti Stammen / so das Hertzogthumb zweyhundert Jahr innen gehabt) tödtlichen Abgang ohne Männliche Leides Lehens Erben / da alsdann Königin Margreta / vorgedachtes Graff Gerharden Nepotem, auch Graff Gerhardt genannt / hinwider damit belehnet / der auch der erste Hertzog von Schleßwig selbiger Linien verblieben / nach dessen absterben haben sich seine Söhne der Cron Dennemarck sehr widerlich bezeiget / darumb jhnen dann auff Begehren König Erichen / als Lehenherrn / vom Keyser Sigismundo / als erwehltten Scheids Richtern / Anno 1415. vnd 1424. propter denegata ab illicitis detentatoribus seruitia, commissam Feloniam & crimen laesae Majestatis, das Hertzogthumb abe vnd dem König zuerkandt worden.**

Als aber hernacher Anno 1431. eine Keyserliche Commission angeordnet / worin sich die Graffen erkläret / dem Könige Fußfall zuthun / Gnade zuzuchen / vnd als gute Fürsten der Cron Dennemarck mit fleiß zu dienen / vnd derselben Mann zuseyn / ist endlich Anno 1435. der Vertrag geschlossen / vnd der König Graff Adolffen das Fürstenthumb Schleßwig / so viel er dessen im Besitz gehabt / Zeit seines Lebens / vnd seinen Erben nach seinem Tode zwey Jahr lang verschrieben / nach absterben aber König Erichen ist Hertzog Adolff von König Christoffern / Hertzogen zu Bayern / mit dem Hertzogthumb Anno 1440. belehnet / welche Belehnung auch hernacher von König Christian dem Ersten / Anno 1445. bekräftiget worden.

Wie aber dieser Hertzog Adolff / als der letzte von Graff Gerharden dieß dritten Stamme / ohne

diesem Stammen etliche wenige zu Fürsten erhoben worden / welche aber nicht jetzige Graffen Progenitores, noch deren Brüdere / sondern in remotiori gradu lineae collateralis ihnen allein verwandt gewesen / ontel welchen Kü hansRELATIONIS HISTORICE Anno dann Graff Gerhardt der Dritte / der erste zum Hertzogen von Schleswig von 1621. Woldimaro Anno 1326. erhöht / welcher aber hernacher das Hertzogthumb Hinwiderumb abtretten / vnnd sich / wie auch seine Söhne / mit der Graffschaffe Holstein vnd den Graffen Titul consentiren lassen müssen / biß auff Hertzog Erichen von Schleswich (der der letzte von Canuti Stammen / sodas Hertzog. thumb zweyhundert Jahr innen gehabt) tödtlichen Abgang ohne manliche Let. bescheus Erben / da alsdann Königin Margreta / vorgedachtes Graff Ger. Hardten Nepotem, auch Graff Gerhardt genandt / hinwider genandt / hinwider damit belehnet / der auch der erste Hertzog von Schleswig selbiger Linien verblieben / nach dessen ab. fterben haben sich seine Söhne der Krone Dennemarcken sehr widerlich bezet get darumb ihnen dann auff begeren König Erichen / als Lehenherzn / vom Keyser Sigismundo /

messrelation_Relationis Hist,
ppn_(DE-627-4)00016741X (1621)
99 dann Graff Gerhardt [...] erumb abtretten / vnnd
99 feine Söhne / mit der [...] en müssen / biß auff

messrelation_Relationis Hist,
ppn_(DE-627-4)005370477 (1621)
99 dann Graff Gerhardt [...] f Hertzog Erichen von

Informationen zur Stelle
Stelle wird 3 Mal von 2 Werken zitiert.
Anzahl Segmente: 4
Zeichenposition: 291917-292230

Segmente der Stelle

Figure 4: Visualisation of text similarities in *Theatrum Europaeum* and the *Meßrelationen* using quid

Still, further work is needed to critically assess these results and conduct further experiments with other genres of potential sources for *Theatrum Europaeum*, e.g. broadsheets or letters. These genres are also used in the VD17 (respective AAD genre terms are *Flugschrift* and *Brief / Briefsammlung*) and can therefore be used to compile additional corpora as described above. These corpora could then be analyzed in relation to the *Theatrum Europaeum* for stylistic similarities and instances of text reuse, e. g. citations from broad sheets and letters, shedding further light on historiographical practices in seventeenth-century Germany. Of course, data from other libraries providing OCR texts of their holdings should also be included to create a more comprehensive dataset, and the workflow above adapted accordingly.

4 Conclusion

Our two exemplary workflows illustrate some of the challenges that arise when using bibliographic data as research data for historical research and steps that can be taken to overcome them. The various standards with different levels of expressiveness and complexity to consider can make it quite challenging to work with this data in a methodologically sound manner. To complicate matters further, the data fields can be populated differently, despite standardisation efforts. This situation results in inconsistencies that necessitate iterative data cleaning and harmonisation steps like those described above to produce valid results. In other words, while overall bibliographic data – and the VD17 in particular – can be regarded as a high-quality data source, like all historical data it is inevitably messy to work with and requires knowledgeable intervention and interpretation to transform into fit-for-purpose research data.

Author Contributions

Maximilian Görmar (Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing--original draft, Writing--review and editing)

Thea Lindquist (Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Validation, Visualization, Writing--original draft, Writing--review and editing)

Eetu Mäkelä (Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing--original draft, Writing--review and editing)

Christoph Boveland (Data curation, Writing--review and editing)

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